

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART X. THE INFLUENCE OF OXYGEN CONCENTRATION ON RANCIDITY

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The effect of pressure of oxygen on the development of rancidity is comparatively insignificant. Relatively small amounts of dissolved oxygen present in fats and oils exert a strong influence on the rancidity. Rancidity by the formation of peroxides of the unsaturated glycerides proceeds in a limited supply of oxygen, which is followed by complete decomposition of the peroxides resulting in the formation of aldehydes at advanced stages. The dissolved oxygen in the fat samples has been measured with the help of van Slyke's apparatus.

The role of oxygen as the fundamental initiator of the process of rancidity in fat has been demonstrated beyond all doubts in the previous papers in the series. The next thing of importance is the concentration of oxygen on the rate of oxidation of fats.

The effect of pressure of oxygen, especially low pressure, on the rate of oxidation of fats is of particular interest because of the present tendency towards storage of fat-containing foodstuffs of various kinds in hermetically sealed containers either under vacuum or inert atmospheres with the obvious object of preventing oxidative rancidity. Unfortunately no work on the effect of pressure of oxygen on the rate of oxidation of fats has yet been published. The present investigation has been devoted to the study of the effect of varying concentration of oxygen within wide limits. The experiments have been divided into (a) effect of pressure of oxygen on the development of rancidity and (b) development of rancidity in limited oxygen supply.

EXPERIMENTAL

Effect of Pressure of Oxygen

The effect of oxygen concentration of the atmosphere of storage in conical flasks, fitted with corks with inlet and outlet tubes connected with stop-cocks was studied. The air in the flasks was displaced by mixtures of oxygen and nitrogen, prepared in desired proportions to give different oxygen concentrations in different aspirator bottles, the passage of the gas being made for sufficiently long time to ensure complete displacement after the flasks had first been evacuated for a short time by means of a high vacuum pump. This study was again divided into two sections: (i) effect of high oxygen pressure, viz. above atmospheric concentration and (ii) effect of low oxygen pressure, viz. below atmospheric concentration. The respective concentrations used were 30%, 40%, 50%, 60%, 75%, 90% and 100% and 15%, 10%, 5%, 3%, 2% and 1%. The progress of rancidity was followed by the determination of Kreis and peroxide values at regular intervals. The gas mixture was replenished fortnightly after each determination in order to keep the concentration constant throughout the experiment. The samples

were stored in a thermostat at 38°. The results are given in Tables I and II and some of these results are shown graphically in Fig. 1. The results of each concentration was checked with duplicate experiment and the mean values are recorded, the variation between the values lying within 5%.

TABLE I

Effect of low oxygen pressure on the development of rancidity in butterfat at 38°.

Expt. No.	Oxygen conc.	Peroxide and ² Kreis values after									
		15 days.		30 days.		45 days.		61 days.		80 days.	
		P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.
1.	Control of air	0.14	0.1	1.10	1.6	2.4	4.2	3.0	8.8	8.0	10.5
2.	15%	0.14	0.2	1.10	1.6	2.35	4.0	2.5	5.0	6.5	7.9
3.	10	0.14	0.2	1.10	1.6	2.20	3.9	2.4	4.6	6.0	7.0
4.	5	0.14	0.2	1.10	1.58	2.1	3.9	2.3	4.6	4.3	7.0
5.	3	0.14	0.2	1.10	1.58	2.0	3.8	2.3	4.4	3.2	6.5
6.	2	0.14	0.2	1.10	1.58	2.0	3.6	2.3	4.2	3.9	6.5
7.	1	0.14	0.2	1.10	1.58	2.0	3.6	2.2	4.0	3.0	6.5

TABLE II

Effect of high oxygen pressure on the development of rancidity in butterfat on storage at 38°.

Expt. No.	Oxygen conc.	Peroxide and Kreis values after									
		15 days.		30 days.		45 days.		60 days.		80 days.	
		P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.
1.	Control in air	0.14	0.1	1.0	1.6	2.4	4.2	3.0	8.8	8.0	10.5
2.	30%	0.14	0.1	1.0	1.6	2.4	4.5	3.30	9.0	8.2	11.0
3.	40	0.14	0.1	1.0	1.6	2.4	5.0	3.87	9.6	9.6	12.0
4.	50	0.14	0.1	1.1	1.65	2.4	5.1	4.12	10.0	10.2	14.0
5.	60	0.14	0.1	1.1	1.85	2.45	6.0	5.4	12.0	12.05	16.2
6.	75	0.14	0.1	1.25	2.0	2.5	6.0	8.0	12.5	12.0	18.1
7.	90	0.14	0.1	1.25	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.15	12.6	12.1	18.0
8.	100	0.14	0.1	1.25	2.1	4.0	7.5	8.5	13.1	15.0	18.1

The effect of decreasing the oxygen content of the atmosphere of storage was found to be almost without effect on the induction period of the fat, *i. e.* fat stored in air as also in an atmosphere of air diluted with different volumes of nitrogen, showed identical induction periods, but the rate of subsequent oxidation was greater in air (Table I).

FIG. 1

The effect of increasing the oxygen concentration from 21% to 100% is that the induction period very nearly remains constant till the atmosphere is completely replaced by one of pure oxygen. The general effect is that the rate of subsequent oxidation has been increased but the results are not so well defined as to distinguish between the various concentrations.

The amount of oxygen required to bring a fat, particularly one like butterfat, containing relatively low proportions of acids, less saturated than oleic, to the end of induction period is very small. It is thus possible that reduction in the pressure of oxygen over a considerable range may produce much less than a proportionate decrease in the oxidation during the induction period. Moreover, the rate of oxidation during this period is controlled by natural antioxidants present in the fat. So also by varying the pressure of oxygen from 21-100%, one fails to obtain a proportionate increase in the oxidation rate, although once the induction period is over the oxidation rate seems to increase somewhat due to an increased concentration of oxygen.

Development of Rancidity in Limited Oxygen Supply

In experiments conducted above, free access of oxygen to the fat was assured. It is of interest to study the case when the total quantity of oxygen available is less than that which can be used up by the fat. For this purpose, the following experiments were conducted:—

(i) Storage of butterfat in a large sealed tube (about 150 c.c. capacity) over a small volume of oxygen.

(ii) Storage in vacuum.

(iii) Storage in inert gas (N_2).

(iv) Storage of butterfat in a large test tube (50 c.c.) completely filled with fat and kept stoppered with a velvet cork, and subsequently sealed with wax.

The mean value of the results of experiments carried out in duplicate are tabulated below (Table III) and graphically in Fig. 2.

TABLE III

Development of rancidity of butterfat in limited oxygen supply.

Expt. No.	Description.	Peroxide and Kreis values after											
		15 days.		30 days.		45 days.		60 days.		75 days.		80 days.	
		P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.	P.V.	K.
1.	Stored in sealed tube (t)	0	0	0.35	1.0	0.65	2.0	1.04	3.3	0.74	2.4	0.25	0.2
2.	Stored in vacuum (tt)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.08	0.80	0.2	1.0
3.	Stored in N ₂ (ttt)	0	0	0.30	1.0	0.60	2.1	1.04	3.2	1.2	4.2	2.0	5.1
4.	Stored in a completely filled test tube (tv)	0	0	0.2	0.8	0.52	2.0	1.0	3.0	0.8	2.7	0.56	0.8
5.	Control in air	0.14	0.1	1.1	1.6	2.1	4.2	3.2	8.8	15.0	10.2	2.30	13.4

It is evident from the above table that the formation of peroxide is very much depressed as compared to the control sample in air. The development of peroxide, however, proceeds slowly with time but after a certain maximum is reached, the peroxide content gradually falls off as the free oxygen is consumed (cf. Fig. 2); secondary changes set in resulting in the decomposition of peroxides. Formation of substance responsible for Kreis test proceeds in the fat stored in a limited oxygen supply until most of the latter and peroxide have been used up. Decomposition by secondary reaction results in a fall and almost total disappearance of the Kreis test (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2 .

That the fat still tastes rancid after storage in limited oxygen supply even after most of the peroxides and Kreis-active substances have undergone decomposition, seems to indicate that volatile aldehydes, mainly responsible for flavour and odour, are stable under these conditions. For this reason, estimation of the contents of volatile

aldehydes that may be responsible for the rancid odour still perceptible in these fat, has been taken recourse to as an additional measure of oxidative rancidity, with a second set of experiments performed in a sealed tube as before. Lea's bisulphite method (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1934 6, 241) has been employed for this purpose and the results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Aldehyde value of butterfat stored in limited oxygen supply.

Expt. No.	Description.	0.002N-I ₂ per gram of fat stored after				
		15 days.	30 days	45 days.	60 days.	80 days.
1.	Stored in sealed tube (f)	0	0.10	0.40	1.40	6.60
2.	Control	0	0.05	0.12	0.50	0.85

The results are shown graphically in Fig. 3. The pronounced lag observed in the appearance of aldehyde, as can be seen from the figure, is of interest in view of the ability of the fat to give rise to secondary products of decomposition from the fat peroxide and the Kreis-active substance.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

From the results in Table III it can be said that rancidity can even proceed in a very limited supply of oxygen. It is thus clear that in order to ensure good protection of fat against rancidity one must be sure that the atmosphere should be free from oxygen. Packages in inert gases seems to have good retarding effect on the rate of oxidation, but since rancidity develops even in strictly inert atmospheres, it is of interest to study the effect of small amounts of oxygen that remains dissolved in fat on the development of rancidity of fats. This effect has been studied in the following section.

Dissolved Oxygen and Rancidity

Development of rancidity slowly proceeds in butterfat even when stored in an inert atmosphere (Table III), though the induction period is very nearly doubled. This points to the fact that in such cases oxidation is brought about by the small amounts of

dissolved oxygen present in the fat itself and so it was considered that estimation of dissolved oxygen during developmet of rancidity might throw light on this problem.

Estimation of Dissolved Oxygen in Butterfat.—There is practically no method of estimating dissolved oxygen in fats and oils in literature. The chemical methods that are prevalent for the estimation of dissolved air in water and sewage, viz. Winkler's and Rideal-Stewart's $MnSO_4$ method (*Per.*, 1888, 21, 2843; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1914, 53, 665) were found unsuitable for this purpose. Polarographic methods of determining dissolved oxygen in liquids cannot be applied in this case due to the non-conducting and non-ionising nature of oils and fats. Recourse was ultimately taken to manometric methods, using van Slyke's apparatus for the estimation of CO_2 and combined oxygen in blood, and this proved very advantageous for the present investigation. The method of estimation as given in the Text Book of Practical Physiological Chemistry" by Hawk and Bergeim (9th Ed., pp. 466-67) was adopted with slight changes suitable for the present purpose. The procedure is detailed below.

By means of a differential pipette 2 c.c. of the fat were transferred directly into the extraction chamber by keeping the tip of the pipette immersed to the bottom of the reagent cup, and regulating the admission by finger and stop-cock below the cup. A few drops of mercury were introduced in the cup as a seal after closing the stop-cock. The apparatus was evacuated and shaken for 3 minutes by slowly driving the wheel by hand. Air-free 1 N-NaOH (1 c.c.) was placed in the cup and the CO_2 absorbed by admitting 0.5 c.c. of the hydroxide into the chamber under diminished pressure. The solution meniscus was brought to either 2 c.c. or 0.5 c.c mark and pressure p_1 (pressure of $O_2 + N_2$) was read. The apparatus was brought again under slight negative pressure by means of the levelling bulb and opening the stop-cock below, 0.5 c.c. of hydrosulphite solution (or alkaline pyrogallate solution) was admitted as before by placing 1.0 c.c. of the absorbent in the cup. One drop was admitted at 5 seconds' intervals consuming 2-3 minutes for the entire absorption; the gas was brought to the same mark as before and p_2 (pressure of N_2) was read on the manometer.

$$P_{O_2} = p_1 - p_2 - c$$

where c is correction for manometric depression caused by introduction of absorbent solution and can be determined from a separate blank experiment. The result is expressed as

$$\text{millimoles gas/litre} = \frac{P \times \text{vol. \% factor}}{2.24}$$

the volume % factor is given in the table by van Slyk. (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, 49, 30).

Attempts to dissolve the fat in a suitable solvent like pyridine or acetone in order to allow the O_2 estimation by absorption in a single reaction phase, however, met with little success, as separation of fat always occurred when absorption of oxygen was effected by addition of alkaline pyrogallol or hydrosulphite solution.

For the present experiments, the butterfat was stored at 37° in an incubator in an atmosphere of nitrogen in conical flasks. The flasks provided with inlet and outlet tubes with stop-cock arrangements, were first evacuated by means of a high vacuum

Cenco pump, filled with N_2 , and by repeating this process of evacuation and refilling with N_2 , complete anaerobic conditions were established. Freshly prepared butterfat was carefully poured in a slow stream inside the flasks carefully avoiding formation of bubbles during the transfer, this precaution being necessary to avoid entrapping air. The flasks were kept stored in the incubator at 37° , keeping necessary control. Progress of rancidity was followed by estimation of Kreis and peroxide values and the amount of dissolved oxygen was estimated with several 2 c.c. portions (usually 3 determinations were made), and mean value tabulated. The results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V

A. Butterfat stored in an atmosphere of N_2 .							
	Original	After 15 days.	After 30 days.	After 45 days.	After 60 days.	After 70 days.	After 80 days.
1. Millimoles O_2 /litre	1.08	1.08	0.98	0.82	0.36	0.0	0.0
2. Millimoles ($N_2 + CO_2$)/litre	4.36	4.36	4.10	4.64	4.36	5.0	5.0
3. Total gas (millimoles/litre)	5.44	5.44	5.08	5.46	4.72	5.0	5.0
4. Peroxide value	0	0	0.20	0.67	1.02	1.62	1.05
5. Kreis No.	0	0	1.0	2.1	3.2	3.2	2.0
B. Control sample.							
1. Millimoles O_2 /litre	1.08	1.08	1.06	0.95	0.76	0.76	0.64
2. Millimoles ($N_2 + CO_2$)/litre	4.4	4.35	4.56	4.56	4.74	4.66	4.65
3. Total gas (millimoles/litre)	5.48	5.43	5.62	5.51	5.50	5.42	5.29
4. Peroxide value	0	0.15	1.0	2.4	3.0	8.0	20.2
5. Kreis No.	0	0.1	1.6	4.2	8.8	10.5	12.0

Estimation of dissolved oxygen during the development of rancidity indicates that increased peroxide formation is accompanied by the an almost proportionate decrease in the amount of dissolved oxygen in the fat. When the whole of oxygen has been used up in peroxide formation, not only further peroxidation is stopped, there is also a subsequent fall in the peroxide content of the fat, due probably to the decomposition of the peroxides already formed. This relationship is clearly shown in Fig. 4, where maximum peroxide formation can be seen to coincide with the minimum oxygen-content (0.0) of the fat.

These experiments along with those performed in a limited oxygen supply go to prove that presence of small amounts of dissolved oxygen is able to produce rancidity in fats, and hence particular care must be taken in ensuring complete removal of this dissolved oxygen when gas packaging is resorted to as a means of preservation of fats from rancidity.

DISCUSSION

It has been shown that very small amounts of oxygen can produce rancidity of fats and the oxygen that remains dissolved in the oil or fat plays a prominent role in the development of rancidity. The effect of increased oxygen pressure is particularly insignificant in view of the relatively small oxygen requirement of the fats (in developing organoleptic rancidity) and the induction period remains constant throughout ; it is only with pure oxygen that a slight decrease in the induction period has been observed. The decreased oxygen pressure is also without effect on the induction period and here also reduction in the pressure of oxygen fails to cause a proportionate decrease in the rate of onset of rancidity and it is only when the oxygen is completely replaced by N_2 , that an increased induction period can be observed. The experiments with limited oxygen supply lead one to the conclusion that the development of rancidity by peroxide formation proceeds so long as there is available oxygen, and when the latter is used up, there can be observed a fall in the concentration of peroxides and also of the Kreis active component due to decomposition reactions. In such cases, the volatile aldehyde content of the fats may give an indication as to the state of rancidity, Kreis and peroxide values being almost negative at the advanced stage in such cases. Estimation of dissolved oxygen in samples, stored in nitrogen atmosphere, shows a gradual fall in the dissolved oxygen content of the fat as rancidity proceeds and ultimately falls to zero, but one interesting point has emerged from these estimations of dissolved gases in that the total gas (millimoles/litre) is very nearly constant throughout the process, both in the control and test sample.

Rancidity may now be ascribed primarily to the action of dissolved oxygen on the unsaturated constituents of the fats and the rate of development of rancidity may be said to depend on the rate of diffusion of oxygen from the atmosphere to the oil, controlled by the solubility of the gas in the fat or oil concerned.

The author gratefully acknowledges his indebtedness to Prof. M. N. Goswami for the keen interest and guidance of the work.